

2687 sequences

0.005 0.01 0.05 0.1 0.5

- ★ **Arthrobacter phage Mudcat (NC_031224) [59,443 nt]**
- ★ **Rhodococcus phage ReqiPoco6 (NC_023694) [78,064 nt]**
- ★ **Rhodococcus phage ReqiPepy6 (NC_023735) [76,797 nt]**
- ★ **Lactococcus phage 1706 (NC_010576) [55,597 nt]**
- ★ **Lactococcus phage P162 (NC_024214) [55,584 nt]**
- ★ **Lactococcus phage P118 (NC_024208) [54,173 nt]**
- ★ **Lactococcus phage P092 (NC_024203) [53,513 nt]**
- ★ **Lactococcus phage P078 (NC_024215) [54,452 nt]**
- Leuconostoc phage P793 (NC_020880) [26,769 nt]**
- Leuconostoc phage phiLN6B (NC_024380) [25,740 nt]**
- Leuconostoc phage Lmd1 (NC_018273) [26,201 nt]**
- Leuconostoc phage phiLN04 (NC_020870) [25,865 nt]**
- Leuconostoc phage phiLN12 (NC_024385) [28,193 nt]**
- Leuconostoc phage phiLN03 (NC_024390) [26,752 nt]**
- Leuconostoc phage phiLN34 (NC_024388) [28,022 nt]**
- Leuconostoc phage phiLNTR3 (NC_024378) [28,015 nt]**
- Leuconostoc phage phiLNTR2 (NC_024389) [28,336 nt]**
- Leuconostoc phage phiLN25 (NC_024386) [28,427 nt]**
- Leuconostoc phage Ln-8 (NC_027377) [28,921 nt]**
- Leuconostoc phage Ln-9 (NC_027358) [28,527 nt]**
- Leuconostoc phage 1-A4 (NC_027987) [29,508 nt]**

Left line: Virus family	
	Siphoviridae (1421)
	Myoviridae (677)
	Podoviridae (431)
	Ackermannviridae (21)
	Rudiviridae (16)
	Others (54)
Right line: Host group	
	Gamma proteobacteria (910)
	Firmicutes (619)
	Actinobacteria (565)
	Cyanobacteria (122)
	Alphaproteobacteria (70)
	Others (224)